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LONG TERM EARTH OBSERVATION MARKET DEVELOPMENT OF ENVISAT-BASED SERVICES

LINE 4: Environmental Information for Marine Operations

ENVISAT MONITORING AND FORECASTING SERVICES FOR OFFSHORE INDUSTRY (EMOFOR)

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DELIVERABLE D-4

Validation report of EO-service chain upgrades for ENVISAT exploitation

And

DELIVERABLE D-5

Examples of improved EO services based on ENVISAT

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1. INTRODUCTION

The EMOFOR services, as described in report D1, D2 and D3, are designed to operate in three different modes and use an integrated system of information from i) satellite remote sensing of the sea surface; ii) in situ measurements of currents as function of time and depth; and iii) 3-D oceanographical fields from ocean models. These are requirements defined by Fugro GEOS and the customers who will use the services. The main capabilities of the service modes are reviewed in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of EMOFOR service modes

Service mode	Service output	Information sources	Service trials
Hindcast mode	Provide statistical information (space and time) about the oceanographic condition in the selected region, especially in the exploration and design phase	Time series of in situ current meter data 3-D model simulations in hindcast Statistics on eddy-kinetic energy from altimetric data	No specific trials planned. Results from previous projects v
Real time mode	Monitor oceanographic fields combining in situ observations and EO-data during installation and production	In situ current data from platform ADCP with real time display Eddy maps from EO data using optimal combination of altimeter, IR/Visual and SAR data	Service trials planned in Northw
Forecast mode	Provide forecasting of extreme events for 1 – 7 days during installation and production	Ocean modelling system using large-scale model nested to high-resolution regional models	Service trial planned in Gulf of M

The EMOFOR services can be classified into four levels varying from low-cost services that are highly automated up to higher cost service cost with increasing human support. The four service levels can be described as:

- 1) *Basic – generic EO-data based service.* Keywords: low-medium resolution (1-5 km), low-cost nowcasting, highly automated, bi-weekly
- 2) *Site-specific nowcasting service.* Keywords: includes i) plus use of SAR, plus use of in situ data, plus GIS data and human analysis.
- 3) *Site-specific forecasting service.* Keywords: includes i) plus ii) plus use of regional, medium-resolution model for 1 – 7 days forecasting,
- 4) *Operational support.* Keywords: includes i) and ii) plus use of high-resolution models for 1 – 7 days forecasting, plus 24 hour telephone support and briefing to operational headquarter.

The service levels are summarised in Table 2:

Table 2: Service level characteristics

Service level	EO -data	EO-data, in situ & analysis	Forecasting: Medium-resolution	Forecasting: High-resolution & operational support	Where service can be provided in 2003
1	x				Global
2	x	x			Global at sites where in situ measurements are obtained
3	x	x	x		Atlantic Ocean, Gulf of Mexico
4	x	x		x	

Two types of service trials will be carried out in 2003. The service trial in Northwest Europe (west Scotland) will be a level 2 service, while the Gulf of Mexico trial will be a level 3 service (Fig. 1). The main technical characterisation of the service trials is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Service trials

Service components to be demonstrated in the trials	<i>Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data</i>	<i>Forecasting from models</i>
Main product	Maps of eddies in 1) Gulf of Mexico 2) Northwest Europe: west Scotland	Forecasted current and other oceanographical fields for 1 – 7 days in Gulf of Mexico
Main customer	Shell: Gulf of Mexico, BP: west Scotland	Shell: Gulf of Mexico
Near real time service	Near real time (within 1 – 2 days)	New forecasts issued every 7 day
Use of EO data	Altimeter, SAR, infrared radiometer, optical images	SST and SLA fields
Which satellites	JASON, ENVISAT, NOAA, etc.	JASON, ENVISAT, NOAA, etc.
Use of <i>in situ</i> current measurements	Yes, from ADCP mounted on the platform	Yes, om ADCP mounted on the platform
Other input data	no	Atmospheric forcing fields and ocean climate data
Product interval	3 – 6 days	weekly

Product format	Maps in standard format agreed with customer	Plots and tabular presentations of current forecasts at specific sites
Product size	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte
Transmission to customers	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail
Service chain established	Yes by CLS for SLA, SST and ocean colour products, by NERSC for SAR	Yes, by NERSC

Figure 1. Map of service trial areas: Northwest Europe (upper map) and Gulf of Mexico (lower map) showing the main current systems.

The purpose of the service trial will be to test the technical performance, verify costs estimates and assess the overall service for further marketing. The trials will be implemented in close co-operation with two oil companies, where trial results will be disseminated to the daily operational briefing meetings onboard platforms. The ocean products from EMOFOR will be presented in a compact manner together with met-info. The primary objective of the Northwest Europe trial will be to improve real-time monitoring with EO data in a challenging area where eddies and fronts move rapidly. Weekly reports of trial results will go to BP. The primary objective of the Gulf of Mexico trial is to demonstrate forecasting of the eddies.

- Use of SST versus ocean colour in Gulf of Mexico: SST will not retrieve eddies in the summer months, whereas ocean colour probably can. This will be clarified in the service trials
- Duration of the service trials: tentatively 3 months
- Training sessions to educate users are planned in association with the planning meeting before start-up service trials
- The feedback to be provided from Shell/BP after the service trials will be used to improve the services before going public
- A free-of-charge demo-period for Shell/BP is foreseen for the service trials over a period of 3 months. A commercial service delivery will start after service trials.
- Sales of services will preferably be by company
- Presentation of results to a wider market: Use the conventions where the companies meet, tentatively twice per year.

Status of ENVISAT data

Since ENVISAT data have not been directly available for use in Phase 1, the service products have been developed with similar data from other satellites, as shown in Table 3. However, preparation for use of ENVISAT RA-2, ASAR, MERIS and AATSR data in the EMOFOR service has been completed. As soon as these data are available on regular basis they can be used to improve the EMOFOR products. Data delivery from two or more satellites will secure the EO data provision in the EMOFOR service.

Table 3 Review of EO data used in EMOFOR

Satellite sensors	Non-ESA data	ESA data	Use in EMOFOR products
Altimetric products	GFO Jason-1	ERS-2 ENVISAT RA-2	SLA maps are used in eddy tracking and as input to forecasting model
Sea surface temperature products	NOAA 14 – 16 AVHRR	ENVISAT AATSR	SST maps are used in eddy tracking and as input to forecasting model
Ocean colour products	SPOT VGT	ENVISAT MERIS	Ocean colour maps are used in eddy tracking, especially when SST is not capable of detecting eddy features
Synthetic Aperture Radar products	RADARSAT SAR	ERS-2 SAR ENVISAT ASAR	Ocean backscatter maps are used to detect eddies under cloudy conditions

2. VALIDATION OF ALTIMETER DATA PRODUCTS AND SERVICE CHAIN

2.1 COMPARISON OF SLA PRODUCTS PROVIDED BY CCAR AND CLS

For several years, CLS (Collecte Localisation Satellite: <http://www.cls.fr>) and CCAR (Colorado Center for Astrodynamics Research: <http://www-ccar.colorado.edu>) produce maps of Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) in Near Real Time (NRT). Note that by NRT, we mean delays of about 1 to 2 days. At present these maps are based on data from the radar altimeters onboard TOPEX/Poséidon (U.S.-French satellite), ERS-2 (European satellite) and GFO (U.S satellite). In the near future, these maps will take into account the data extracted from radar altimeters onboard Jason (French- U.S. satellite) and ENVISAT (European satellite). An overview of the altimeter satellites to be used in EMOFOR is given in Table 4. Some qualitative comparison of the CCAR products and the CLS products are presented in this section.

Table 4: Satellite used by CCAR and CLS processing systems

Satellite	T/P	ERS-2	GFO	Jason	ENVISAT
Country	USA/France	Europe	USA	USA/France	Europe
User	NASA, JPL, CNES	ESA	US Navy	NASA, JPL, CNES	ESA
Size	~10 m long	~11 m long	~3 m long	~3 m long	26 m long
Mass	2442 kg	2516 kg	300 kg	500 kg	8211 kg
Date launch	10 Aug 1992	21 Apr 1995	10 Feb 1998	7 Dec 2001	1 Mar 2002
Orbit altitude	1336 km	800 km	880 km	1336 km	800 km
Inclination	66°	98.5°	108°	66°	98.5°
Repeat period	10 days	35 days	17 days	10 days	35 days

2.2 DATA USED BY CCAR AND CLS

Data processing centre

CCAR and CLS developed two different systems to process Near Real Time (NRT) multi-mission altimeter data:

- A) “quick-look mesoscale processing” for CCAR
- B) SSALTO/DUACS for CLS

The types of global products delivered by CCAR and CLS (available on their respective websites) are the global maps of SLA, as shown in Fig. 2a and b, using the same colour scale for the two products.

TOPEX/ERS-2 Analysis Mar 27 2002

a)

SSALTO/DUACS – NRT MSLA – Merged Product
2002/03/27

b)

Figure 2: a) CCAR global map of SLA; b) CLS global map of SLA, using the same colour scale

At a first glance, the maps seem to be the same except the latitude coverage of the data which is limited in the CCAR product (-62°S to 62°N) and not in the CLS product (data are represented north and south if available remote sensing measurement are present). In the following, several areas will be focused on to allow a better comparison in local areas.

Data sources

The operational systems which deliver NRT data to produce maps of SLA need fast-delivery data. To construct these maps, the systems provide the user with the difference between the (corrected) rough measurements and the satellite orbit computed by external services (such as CNES, DEFLT institute and NOAA). These NRT data are provided by different sources depending on the satellites:

- TOPEX, Poséidon, GFO, Jason and ENVISAT: Interim Geophysical Data Records (IGDR);
- ERS-2: Fast Delivery Products (FDP).

The computation time and acquisition of the fast-delivery data of the satellite orbits govern the overall time availability of the maps of SAL. Table 5 and 6 present the characteristics of the CCAR and CLS input data overview. For Jason-1 and ENVISAT the CCAR input data were not available.

Table 5: CCAR input data overview

<i>CCAR</i>			
Altimetric product	Source	Availability	Type of orbit
TOPEX IGDR	Navocean	48h	JPL/PO.DAAC- NOAA
Poséidon IGDR	Not used	-	-
ERS-2 FDP	NOAA	24 to 36 h	DELFT JGM-3
GFO IGDR	NOAA	72h	NOAA MOE
Jason IGDR	?	?	?
ENVISAT	?	?	?

Table 6: SSALTO/DUACS input data overview

CLS

Altimetric product	Source	Availability	Type of orbit
TOPEX IGDR	Navocean / AVISO	48h	CNES MOE
Poséidon IGDR	AVISO	48h	CNES MOE
ERS-2 FDP	Météo France	Less than 24h	DELFT MOE
GFO IGDR	NOAA	72h	NOAA MOE
Jason IGDR	AVISO	48h	CNES MOE
ENVISAT IGDR	AVISO	48h	CNES MOE

2.3 DATA PROCESSING

As the trajectories of the satellites provide along-track data, several steps have to be undertaken to get the gridded maps of SLA. To obtain these maps based on altimeter data from different satellites, two main operations have to be performed:

- 1) Orbit error corrections (to adjust the satellites data onto each other before mapping);
- 2) Joint mapping of the corrected data sets (to get gridded SLA from along-track data).

For those two steps, CCAR and CLS processing are quite different.

CCAR processing

As mentioned in *Leben et al.* [2002], all along-track altimeter data are referenced to an independent gridded Mean Sea Surface (MSS) by subtracting the MSS value at the sub-satellite point from each observation. An updated version of the MSS is used in the processing: the GSFC00.1 MSS [*Wang, 2001*]. Then, CCAR uses a simple orbit error correction scheme based on along-track Loess filtering to remove residual orbit and environmental correction errors. This “quick-look analysis” [*Leben and Born, 2002*] is designed to retain the mesoscale signal while removing the substantial orbit error that may be present in the fast-delivery products [*Lillibridge et al., 1997*].

This processing technique is known to eliminate large-scale ocean signals, such as the seasonal signal due to the thermal expansion/contraction of the water. Other signals associated with large-scale phenomena like the El Niño can also be seriously affected. This technique can also alter the mesoscale signal, in particular in regions where this signal is weak and in regions where the shape of the coast is complex such as enclosed seas.

Then, CCAR uses a classical Objective Analysis (OA) method to perform the gridded mapping of the corrected data sets from along-track corrected altimeter data. To compute the maps of SLA, CCAR developed an iterative difference-correction scheme initially developed to analyze atmospheric data fields for weather analysis [*Cressman, 1959*]. A fast multi-grid preconditioned

Cressman analysis [*Hendricks et al.*, 1996] with temporal weighting is used to objectively interpolate the along-track data to a $1/4^\circ$ grid. The most recent 10 days of T/P data and 17 days of ERS-2 and GFO data are used in the analysis with a 12-day decorrelation time scale for temporal weighting.

CLS processing

Since 1990, CLS developed and improved highly precise orbit error correction schemes and mapping techniques that are now used in the SSALTO/DUACS project. Application and products in oceanography are derived from these maps [*Lefèvre et al.*, 2002]. The main characteristics of the CLS processing are divided in two main steps:

The orbit error correction scheme is based on a global minimization of the crossover differences between TOPEX and ERS-2 [*Le Traon et al.*, 1995; *Le Traon and Ogor*, 1998].

The mapping technique has been specifically devised to take into account the unusual structure of the altimetric measurement errors, and in particular of the residual orbit error [*Le Traon et al.*, 1998].

As shown in the different papers quoted above, these data processing techniques leave the original altimetric signal almost unaffected. In particular, the mesoscale features and the seasonal signal are present in CLS maps. These signals are most certainly useful to interpret small-scale variations such as eddies for the offshore industry and the seasonal variations for the fishing activity. Moreover these maps are of very good quality in enclosed seas such as the Mediterranean Sea [*Ayoub et al.*, 1998] or more generally in regions where the shape of the coast is complex, which would invalidate the results if simple error reduction techniques were applied.

Recent improvements have been completed in the SSALTO/DUACS processing system:

- Maps of SLA are now provided relative to a 7-year mean (1993-1999 from TOPEX/POSEIDON and ERS data) the Mean Sea Surface (MSS) CLS01 [*Hernandez et al.*, 2001];
- A new tidal model (GOT99) is used to improve geophysical corrections [*Ray*, 1999];
- A new improved inverse barometer correction using a variable time mean pressure is used to improve geophysical corrections [*Dorandeu and Le Traon*, 1999];
- Improved processing algorithms for orbit error reduction and mapping are used. In particular an improved statistical description (covariance) of noise and ocean signal which take into account space and time scales and propagation velocities derived from T/P and ERS data [*Ducet et al.*, 2000; *Le Traon et al.*, 2002];
- Geosat Follow On (GFO) data are now included in the routine processing [*Le Traon et al.*, 2002] to improve the description of the mesoscale ocean circulation.

High resolution maps of SLA (one file per week and per satellite plus one combining all the satellites) on a $1/3^\circ$ MERCATOR grid. The map is obtained via a global space/time optimal interpolation method that takes into account correlated noise. Noise and signal covariances depend

on geographical position. The improved CLS processing system generates maps of SLA by using long time intervals over which the data are gathered before processing. Indeed this system uses time scales which depend on the coordinate of the each considered point of the gridded maps. For the three satellites (T/P, ERS-2 and GFO) the time correlation scales are between 10 days to more than 50 days.

2.4 MAIN DIFFERENCES BETWEEN CCAR AND CLS MAP PROCESSING

The previous paragraph presents the characteristics of the two processing systems used to generate maps of SLA from along-track altimeter data. This paragraph summarises the main differences between the CCAR and CLS processing systems:

The MSS used by CCAR is the GSFC00.1 MSS whereas CLS uses the CLS01 MSS. A recent report [*Hernandez and Schaeffer, 2001*] shows that at small wavelengths, the CLS01 MSS stays closer to the mean profiles, which means that the short scales of the geoid undulations are better mapped than in the GSFC00.1 MSS. This allows the mesoscale features to be better represented with the CLS MSS. CCAR removes the orbit error by a spatial Loess filter whereas CLS developed and uses a specific algorithm (based on a global minimization of the crossover differences between T/P, ERS-2 and GFO).

The CCAR objective analysis algorithm is a “quick-look mesoscale processing” whereas the CLS one is specifically devised to take into account the unusual structures of the altimetric measurement errors, and the residual orbit errors.

Compared to the CCAR processing system CCAR use to generate maps of SLA, the improved CLS processing system uses longer time intervals over which the data are gathered before processing. Indeed CLS performed tests that led CLS to make a significantly different choice than CCAR.

CCAR products are presented on $1/4^\circ$ grids. CLS products are distributed on $1/3^\circ$ Mercator grid. However for local studies the CLS grids can be refined to better represent mesoscale variability. CCAR products are delivered every 3 days. CLS global products are delivered each week. However, for global or local studies the CLS maps of SLA can distributed at more frequent intervals (each day for example). The coverage of the CCAR processing system is between -62°S and 62°N whereas the coverage of the CLS one is global (-90°S to 90°N where altimeter data are present).

Examples: SLA maps of 27 March 2002

To highlight the differences, which occur in the data processing by CLS and CCAR, several maps of SLA are presented for selected local areas, as shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5:

- The Gulf of Mexico;

-
- The Northwest Atlantic Ocean near European coasts;
 - The Gulf of Guinea near the west African coast.

A common date of computation was selected: 27 March 2002. Colour scales, ticks mark on colour bar and contouring are identical between the two maps of the different areas. Several qualitative remarks can be formulated while looking at the maps.

Gulf of Mexico

TOPEX/ERS-2 Analysis Mar 27 2002

a)

b)

Figure 3: a) CCAR NRT Map of SLA; b) CLS NRT Map of SLA, both in the Gulf of Mexico

For the Gulf of Mexico, the SLA appears smoothed in the CCAR maps compared to the CLS maps. This is a result of the Loess filter used in the CCAR processing, which spatially smooths the surface whereas CLS algorithm takes into account the small oceanic scales. Thus, the CCAR computations can underestimate the maxima of SLA, which leads to computation of smoother

slopes of the SLA. As a result the geostrophic currents, which can be computed from the maps of SLA, would also be underestimated compared to the CLS processing system.

Northwest Atlantic Ocean

For the Northwest Atlantic Ocean, the CCAR data are cut at 60°N and the objective analysis creates artifacts at the northern boundary (very small features which are not correlated with the oceanic signal). CLS coverage (fully global) prevents this type of problem.

TOPEX/ERS-2 Analysis Mar 27 2002

a)

b)

Figure 4: a) CCAR NRT Map of SLA; b) CLS NRT Map of SLA, both in the Northwest Atlantic Ocean and North Sea area

Gulf of Guinea

For the Gulf of Guinea, the CCAR map appears to be more noisy compared to the CLS map, as seen in Figure 5. To investigate this further, the Sea Surface Height computed by the MERCATOR group (<http://www.mercator.com.fr/>) for the 27 March 2002 is represented in Figure 6.

a)

b)

Figure 5: a) CCAR NRT Map of SLA; b) CLS NRT Map of SLA in the Gulf of Guinea

initial sea surface height : SSH on 27-03-2002 near 0m

Figure 6: SSH computed by the MERCATOR group

It can be seen that the small structures, which are present in the CCAR product are not present in CLS and MERCATOR products. This fact cannot be explained at the present time. But, although the MSS reference is not the same between MERCATOR SSH and CLS map of SLA, the CCAR small features do not occur in these two first products. It can be assumed that these structures, which are shown in the CCAR map, are not physically present in the ocean.

Moreover, in the CCAR map, a problem of continuity takes place around the Greenwich meridian. CLS processing system prevents this problem: the continuity of the maps of SLA is provided across the Greenwich meridian.

2.5 CONCLUSION

This section has presented a qualitative comparison of the processing systems developed by CCAR and CLS, which generate Near Real Time maps of Sea Level Anomaly from T/P, ERS-2 and GFO data. It was not feasible to provide quantitative results as the CCAR maps are only accessible as GIF images and not data. The report is only focused on qualitative comparative results.

Several differences were highlighted between the two processing systems. In particular, it has been demonstrated that the approach of the CLS system to produce maps, which represent the mesoscale variations of the sea surface, is superior. The knowledge and the prediction of oceanic mesoscale features is a key element in developing services for offshore applications and fishery activities that provide major cost savings by helping in operational decision making and by increasing safety during offshore operations.

3. VALIDATION OF SAR IMAGES FOR USE IN EDDY TRACKING

3.1 TEMPORAL AND SPATIAL COVERAGE OF THE SATELLITE IMAGES

An important issue in use of satellite images is how to obtain optimal sampling in space and time. For near-polar orbiting satellites, three factors determine the mean time interval, T_m , between data coverage of an observation position:

- The swath width of the instrument: T_m decreases with increasing swath width.
- The latitude of the observation position: T_m decreases towards the poles (roughly proportional to cosine of the latitude).
- The operational schedule, or how often the instrument is turned "on": T_m decreases with increasing instrument "on-time".

The AVHRR scanning radiometers onboard the NOAA-12 and NOAA-14 are always turned on and cover the equator 2 times per day, but more frequently at higher latitudes. At every pass, the

instrument swath covers an area more than 2,500 km wide, but the performance is reduced at the swath edges. A scene is about 2,000 km wide and approximately 1,600 km long, centered on the satellite subtrack. At Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS), the majority of the AVHRR scenes of interest are processed to images and archived for later distribution.

The temporal and spatial sampling is much more sparse for the ERS SAR system compared to RADARSAT and ENVISAT which provide much wider swaths. With a swath width of only 100 km, a given position at 65°N can only be imaged every six days on average by the ERS SAR if the instrument is always turned on. At present, the instrument is turned on and off by command, and is generally turned off for northbound (ascending) passes. This means the average revisit interval is 12 days, if all descending passes are turned on. As the turn-on time is also limited by power constraints and largely determined by demands from customers, descending passes may also have the SAR instrument turned off. Consequently, the mean sampling interval will be further lengthened. The ENVISAT ASAR will be subject to similar constraints, but the coverage of a given site will be improved by use of the Wide Swath Mode.

The main limiting factor in using AVHRR images for observation of the ocean surface in all Norwegian waters is the frequent cloud cover. Even a thin or scattered cloud cover will make observations of the surface difficult or impossible. Off mid-Norway, an average cloud cover of more than 80% can be expected for long periods of the year. Especially in the autumn and winter seasons this area is frequently obscured by clouds.

SAR data, on the other hand, provide good quality images of the sea surface for all cloud and light conditions. But the capability of the SAR to observe the sea surface is dependent on a suitable wind speed interval. The best conditions for imaging is found for wind speeds roughly between 2 m/s and 8 m/s. Outside of this interval, the necessary modulation of the capillary waves to observe current signatures is usually not present. Too weak and too strong wind will result in very dark and very bright homogeneous images, respectively. This constraint limits the proportion of good observations to 30-50% of all SAR images available. The highest probability to find useful SAR images for the Norwegian study area is in the summer (April - September), because then the winds are more gentle than in the winter season.

3.2 VALIDATION OF SAR EDDY TRACKING OFF THE COAST OF NORWAY

An eddy tracking study was performed off the coast of Norway based on analysis of archived ERS SAR data obtained for a period of 20 months (November 1996 through June 1998). The eddy tracking area was defined to be between about 62°N and 68°N, and between the Norwegian coast and 0°E. Of special interest are areas where drilling for oil has been planned (e.g. Ormen Lange), and positions/sections where other current measurements have been made near-simultaneously (e.g. the Svinøy Section off Møre).

All processed SAR scenes were available as digital files in LRI¹-format. A total of 63 SAR scenes were selected for analysis. Consecutive ERS SAR scenes have been concatenated to form the 33 images (stripes). The spatial distribution of the SAR images in the study area was non-homogeneous, because there had been no systematic acquisition of images. In a future monitoring project it will be necessary to acquire SAR images systematically over a given region. The analysis of the study is summarised in Table 7, and the main conclusions were the following:

- 1) Fronts or eddies are seen as curved dark or bright current related line features without occurrence of slicks. The background usually has the same backscatter level on both sides of the feature. Line features can be caused by zones of current shear or by current convergence/divergence, which affect the capillary waves and thereby the SAR backscatter. An example of this type of image is shown in Figure 7 a.
- 2) Elongated dark lines of slicks show surface current patterns including eddies without clear fronts. Biological surface material generate slicks which act as tracers for the water motion, especially in the spring and summer. An example of this type of image is shown in Figure 7 b.

¹ LRI - Low Resolution Image, pixel size approx. 100m in range and 80m in azimuth.

*Figure 7. a) Current and eddy features in the ERS-2 image 30 May 1998, covering 100 by 100 km;
b) ERS-2 SAR image covering the Ormen Lange field, obtained on 22 April 1998, showing intense eddy activity. Note the stronger backscatter signal area in the lower left part of the image caused by stronger wind here. ©ESA/TSS, 1998*

Table 6. Current features analysis of the SAR images

Image no.	Image date	Ocean fronts					Current pattern without fronts		Eddies			Comments
		# of fronts	length (km)	orientation	Bright Front	dark front	turbulent field	orientation	# cyclonic	# anti-cyclonic	scale (km)	
1	10.11.96	no					no		-	-		only atmospheric features
2	29.11.96	1	30	N-S	X		no		-	-		mainly atmospheric features
3	19.01.97	15-20	5-100	NW-SE SW-NE	many	a few	no		-	-		
4	14.03.97	8-12	5-80	SW-NE	many	a few	no		-	-		
5	07.05.97	10-20	5-30	all	many	a few	no	EW + all	3 - 5	1	5 - 30	
6	23.05.97	3-5	10-50	N-S	X	X	no		2	-	10 - 20	
7	01.06.97	3-5	10-20	N-S	-	X	yes	all	3 - 4	1	10 - 30	
8	08.06.97	2-3	10-20	E-W	X	X	yes	all	7 - 8	1 - 2	5 - 30	
9	11.06.97	no					yes	all	8 - 10	3 - 4	10 - 40	eddies visible due to slicks
10	19.06.97	no					yes	all	3	-	5 - 40	most of image covered by winds
11	13.07.97	no					yes	all	yes	yes	> 5	turbulent eddy field dominates
12	16.07.97	4-6	20-30	N-S E-W	-	X	yes	all	6 - 7	1 - 2	10 - 50	well-defined eddies, internal waves
13	19.07.97	3-5	20-50	N-S E-W	-	X	little		5 - 6	-	10 - 40	well-defined eddies
14	01.08.97	3-5	20-30	N-S	X	X	yes	all	3 - 4	-	20 - 30	also small scale eddies < 5 km
15	30.08.97	10-15	20-50	N-S	many	-	no	SE - NW	2 - 3	-	5 - 10	
16	24.09.97	8-10	20-40	all	X	X	no		4 - 5	-	10 - 20	
17	27.09.97	10-12	10-100	SW-NE	X	X	little	S - N	3 - 4	-	10 - 20	
18	22.12.97	> 20	10-50	all	X	X	little	all	4 - 5	-	10 - 30	
19	15.01.98	6-8	10-50	all	X	X	little		1	-	20	
20	26.01.98	6-8	10-50	all	X	X	no		-	-		
21	24.02.98	5-6	20-50	SW-NE NW-SE	X	X	no		-	-		
22	02.03.98	4-5	10-40	all	X	-	no		-	-		internal waves
23	08.03.98	6-8	20-50	SW-NE NW-SE	X	X	no		1	-	20	
24	19.04.98	no					yes	all	5 - 6	-	5 - 20	
25	19.04.98	4-5	10-50	all	X	X	no		3 - 4	-	10 - 20	
26	22.04.98	no					yes	all	6 - 7	-	10 - 30	cyclonic eddy also visible in AVHRR image
27	05.05.98	4-5	10-30	E-W			little	all	5 - 6	1 - 2	10 - 20	
28	08.05.98	no					yes	all	4 - 5	-	10 - 30	convective cells
29	16.05.98	2-3	20-30	NW-SE	X	X	little	EW	2 - 3	1	5 - 30	possible oil slick
30	30.05.98	4-5	20-50	NW-SE	X	-	little	SW-NE	2 - 3	-	10 - 20	
31	12.06.98	3-4	20-30	all	X	X	yes	all	-	-		internal waves
32	12.06.98	4-5	20-50	ALL			no		1	0	30	eddy can also be wind cyclone
33	24.06.98	no					little		0	1	30	

The main results of the SAR analysis were:

- 1) Ocean fronts were seen in about 75% of the SAR images, with a typical length of 20-40 km. In about half of these images, the fronts were oriented in 1-2 predominant directions (NW-SE and SW-NW).
- 2) Current patterns due to slicks were observed in nearly 60 % of the SAR images. The current patterns showing the mesoscale flow field were most frequently found from April to August, since slicks are observed more frequently in the spring and summer. The orientation of the features appeared to be random.
- 3) Eddies were observed in about 75 % of the SAR images. Typical horizontal scale of the eddies was 10-30 km, and the rotation was cyclonic for most of the eddies. In one case the mean propagation speed over a 3-day period was estimated to be 18 cm/s for one cyclonic eddy.
- 4) Comparison of satellite observed features with bottom topography showed that the maximum occurrence of fronts and eddies was found along the shelf break from 62.5° N to 65° N and from 66.5° N to 67.5° N. This area coincides with the core of the North-Atlantic current as observed by a moored current meter array.
- 5) Analysis of a series of SAR images can give statistical information about eddy propagation. A similar technique can be used for monitoring and detection of eddies using SAR data in near real time.

3.3 COMPARISON OF SAR EDDY TRACKING WITH ALTIMETER AND IN SITU DATA

SAR versus altimeter observations

Joint use of altimeter derived eddy observations and SAR image analysis can be a useful combination of two independent data sources. A direct comparison can be difficult because the temporal and spatial coverage and resolution of the two systems are quite different. While SAR is capable of observing snapshots of features with scales down to a few hundreds of meters, the altimeter provides sea level height anomalies along the satellite tracks with a sampling distance of about 7 km. By combining data from several tracks over a time interval of at least 10 days, it is possible to establish geostrophic velocity anomaly maps resolving current features with scales of a few tens of kilometers. This implies that the altimeter can observe current features which are persistent and stationary over at least 10 days. Altimeter data cannot capture short-lived mesoscale features observed by SAR. On the other hand, the temporal SAR sampling, which is at best three days for the ERS system, is not good enough to follow the evolution of the short-lived features.

The temporal sampling is also a problem in deriving the altimeter sea level anomalies. The lack of an adequate geoid makes it necessary to subtract a temporal mean from the altimeter height measurements. The 10 (35) day sampling interval of the TOPEX/Poseidon (ERS) altimeter is hardly adequate to resolve mesoscale variability in the Norwegian study area, where temporal scales of eddies can be as short as a few days. Consequently, the mean that is subtracted from the time series of sea level measurements will be contaminated by variability at these unresolved temporal scales.

Since SAR is a side-looking instrument and altimeter is a nadir-looking instrument, it is not feasible to obtain simultaneous observations from the two instruments from the same satellite. In the study off the coast of Norway it has been possible to use altimeter tracks of the T/P crossing ERS-2 SAR

swath within 1-2 days of each other. This approach has been used to compare SAR current feature images with geostrophic current estimates from altimeter data. The same approach will be used with ENVISAT ASAR in combination with altimeter data from T/P and JASON.

Example of joint observations of eddies by SAR and altimetry

The ERS-2 SAR image acquired over an area southwest of Ormen Lange on 27. Sept 1997 is shown in Figure 8. It shows very clear frontal structures, associated with mesoscale eddies. The altimeter track no. 144 of TOPEX/Poseidon crosses these features about 6 hours before the SAR image was taken. This altimeter profile indicates a frontal zone with southward velocities in the left part of the image and northward velocities in the right part. Also the 10-day averaged mapped geostrophic velocity field is superimposed on the image, showing a cyclonic eddy in the lower part of the image. This eddy agrees with the instantaneous data from the single altimeter track as well as with the features in the SAR image.

Figure 8. ERS-2 SAR image acquired on 27.09.97 overlaid with altimeter along-track anomalies (coloured dots), and cross-track geostrophic velocity anomalies (green arrows) on 27.09.9 and mapped geostrophic velocity anomalies (red arrows) for the period 21.09.97 to 01.10.97.

Example of joint observations of eddies by SAR and current meter moorings

An array of four moorings with Aanderaa current meters have been operated by Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen for several years along the Svinøy Section (SS) off the coast of Norway. The current meters have been deployed at depths of 100m, 300m and near the bottom. In order to compare eddy observations in SAR images with in situ measurements, current data taken at the same time and location as the SAR images are extracted and compared with features in the SAR images. Data from the uppermost current meter, usually at 100 m depth, has been used in the comparison.

The SAR image in figure 9 shows a larger cyclonic eddy north of the 3 current moorings and a smaller cyclonic eddy between S2 and E1. S2 measured 40 cm/s in direction toward 45°, which is about 30° clockwise relative to the direction of the current-lines southeast of the eddy center. E1 measured

15 cm/s in direction 270°, which is in good agreement with the current lines north of the same eddy. E2 measured 15 cm/s in direction 260° in an area without clear line features. It should be noted that a direct comparison of Eulerian point measurements at 100 m depth with an instantaneous surface picture is not necessarily valid. But it can offer a certain qualitatively assessment of the SAR observations

Figure 9. The SAR image obtained over the current mooring array on 19 June 1997 is overlaid with current vectors obtained at the same time as the SAR image. The long arrow indicates the north direction..

4. STATUS OF THE SERVICE CHAIN FOR EO DATA PRODUCTS FROM CLS

This chapter briefly presents the data acquisition systems which are operational at CLS for the EMOFOR project:

- **Altimetry products**
- **Sea surface temperature products**
- **Ocean colour products**

The chapter also presents the system in term of personnel, data storage and computers. ENVISAT data (RA-2, AATSR and MERIS) have not yet been included, but the system is ready for ingesting these data as soon as they are available.

4.1 ALTIMETRY DATA PROCESSING

The purpose of the Ssalto/Duacs system is to produce Near Real Time (NRT) along-track Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) and NRT maps of SLA combining data from different altimetric missions (ERS-2, GFO and Jason satellites at the present time, ENVISAT in a near future).

4.1.1 Data

Four types of altimetric data are envisioned in the future processing system:

- ERS-2 altimetric data are real time FDP data
 - GFO data are daily IGDR files provided by NOAA with a preliminary MOE orbit
 - Jason-1 data are delivered by the Ssalto/CMA data server
 - Envisat will be delivered by the Ssalto/CMA data server
-
- Other types of various data are used in the processing chain:
 - The 24 hour ERS-2 orbit is computed by the Delft University with dgm-e04.
 - The pressure correction grids from the ECMWF model are provided by Meteo France
 - The wet tropospheric correction grids from the ECMWF model are provided by Meteo France
 - The pole tide is computed from IERS data.

4.1.2 Overview of the Ssalto/Duacs system

The main Ssalto/Duacs processing steps are:

- Acquisition of altimetric data from various altimeter missions in near real time;
- Validation and correction of the altimetric data sets (edition and selection, update of corrections and homogenisation, orbit error reduction);
- Production of along-track Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) data for each mission;
- Production of maps of Sea Level Anomaly (MSLA) (NRT data from all missions are merged into a single map using optimal interpolation and accounting for Long Wavelength errors)

An overview of the whole acquisition system is shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Ssalto/Duacs System overview

Three different kinds of processing are performed in the Ssalto/Duacs system:

- continuous processing (acquisition system);
- daily processing (data enhancement and validation, crossover determination);

- weekly processing (product generation).

Acquisition

The acquisition software detects, downloads and processes incoming data as soon as they are available on remote sites (external database, ftp site...). Data are split into passes if necessary (ERS and GFO data input format do not include any Cycle/Pass information). Altimetric data are then synchronized with Dynamic Auxiliary Data such as ERS-2 orbit, pressure and tropospheric correction from ECMWF model fields or pole tide correction. This processing step delivers "raw" data, that is to say data that have been divided into cycles and passes, and ordered chronologically.

Processing

The main steps of the daily processing consist in data update and enhancement and computation of the crossover data set. Homogeneous geophysical corrections and fields are computed for each altimetric measurement. For instance, the GOT99 ocean tide correction is present in Jason-1 products but Topex/Poseidon, ERS-2 or GFO data need to be updated with this specific tide correction. Various corrections or homogeneous fields are also computed from other Static Auxiliary Data : CLS 2000 Mean Sea Surface], inverse barometer correction using time-varying reference pressure... Various Cal/Val algorithms are then used on the raw data sets. Then an editing procedure removes data according to validation criteria and methods (quality flags, thresholds, spline fit, abnormal SSH slope detection...).

Mono-satellite and multi-satellite crossover determination is performed on a daily basis. All altimeter fields (measurement, corrections and other fields such as bathymetry, MSS...) are interpolated at crossover locations and dates. This crossover data set will be the input of the Orbit Error Reduction (OER) method in the product generation processing step.

4.1.3 Involved personnel

A team of two experts is full-time involved to run the Ssalto/Duacs system. They:

- Collect the input data
- Validate the input data before processing them
- Process the chain
- Check the processing of the system
- Validate the output data before their distribution
- Make improvements if needed
- Add new input data if available
- Provide an assistance to end users

The computations are done on internal CLS PC workstations under Linux environment.

4.2 SEA SURFACE TEMPERAURE AND OCEAN COLOUR DATA PROCESSING

4.2.1 Data treatment of the GAC AVHRR (Sea Surface Temperature)

The acquisition of level 1B GAC AVHRR is an automatic process as soon as data are available at NOAA. Data are set as orbit segment. 14 files are upload each day. Only data during night are downloaded (descending tracks of NOAA14 or NOAA16). By default, the geographic projection is stereo polar. On an equatorial band, 150 mega octets of level 1B data are produced each day for the NOAA16 satellite.

Figure 11: Sea surface temperature system overview

For each level 1B a level 2 file is processed. Data are projected and interpolated on regular Cartesian grids (0.04°x0.04°).

4.2.2 Data treatment of the SPOT data (Ocean Colour)

The acquisition of level 1B VGT data is an automatic process as soon as data are available at VITO (Belgium). Data are set as orbit segment. 14 files are upload each day. Only data during daylight are downloaded (ascending tracks of SPOT satellite). Input data are distributed on a 0.0089°x0.0089° grid (that is to say 1km at the equator). On an equatorial band, 500 mega octets of level 1B data are produced each day for the SPOT.

Figure 12: Ocean colour system overview

For each level 1B a level 2 file is processed. Data are projected and interpolated on regular Cartesian grids (0.01°x0.01°).

4.3 INVOLVED PERSONNEL

Another team of two expert persons is full-time involved to run these two systems. They:

- Check the collection the input data and act if necessary
- Validate the input data before processing them
- Check the processing of the system
- Process level1B to level 2 data
- Validate the output data before their distribution
- Make improvements if needed
- Provide an assistance to end users

The computations are done on internal CLS PC workstations

5. STATUS OF THE SERVICE CHAIN FOR SAR DATA PRODUCTS FROM NERSC

5.1 DATA ACQUISITION AND PROCESSING

5.1.1 SAR data receiving stations

SAR data from RADARSAT and ENVISAT will be acquired from Tromsø Satellite Station in Northern Norway for the EMOFOR service development. This SAR station covers Northern Europe including the area between Faroe Islands and Scotland, where the service trial will be performed (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. SAR receiving masks for the North Atlantic region for the Canadian station in Gatineau (a), the West Freugh station in UK (b), Tromsø Satellite Station and the ESA station in Kituna (c/d).

Figure 14. Overlap of ENVISAT MERIS, AATSR and ASAR modes

5.1.2 Geometric and radiometric processing of ERS and ENVISAT SAR data

The SAR processing steps for ERS and RADARSAT will be used on ENVISAT ASAR data as soon as they become available. The processing steps are described as follows: The first step is to perform geometric and radiometric correction, which include calibration, resulting in a uniform data set. SAR image pixels are resampled to appropriate pixel size and adjacent scenes are merged to cover the required area. For ERS SAR we use typical 100 m square size, and adjacent scenes of 100 x 100 km concatenated to make larger images, called stripes, which each consisted of 1-4 scenes. Grid lines were overlaid with a grid accuracy of 1-2km. Wideswath scenes data may not need to be concatenated because one scene is usually large enough to cover the monitoring area.

For ERS the incidence angle, theta, is varying from 19.5° to 26.5° across the 100 km swath width of the image. Normalisation of the backscatter signal was performed crosstrack (in range direction), correcting for three effects: (1) antenna gain, (2) slant range and (3) sin(theta) (Laur et al., 1993, 1996). After this procedure, the SAR data are calibrated to an accuracy of approximately ±1.5dB. For image display purposes, the known variation of the backscatter with theta was also compensated (using the inverse sin(theta) to the 4th power), with reference to the midrange theta of 23°. At midrange, the conversion to the backscatter coefficient σ_0 , also called sigma-zero, is given in dB as follows:

$$\sigma_0 = 20 * \log (W) - 48$$

where W is the pixel value in the image after conversion from LRI to 8-bit imf format. Similar procedure for radiometric and geometric processing will be followed for ASAR images as soon as they become available.

5.1.3 Feature interpretation in SAR images

In SAR images, data are created by the return signal, which is a fraction of the emitted signal from the SAR. This fraction, called backscatter coefficient or sigma-zero, is mainly determined by the wave roughness on a scale around 6 cm of the water surface, which is close to the wavelength of the C-band SAR instrument onboard the ERS-2 satellite. Waves on this scale are called capillary waves or Bragg waves, and are caused by the near-surface wind. The capillary waves and thus the backscatter signal are modulated by many sea surface processes, such as long ocean waves, precipitation, internal waves, current shear, current divergence and convergence, and by slicks of surface material of various kinds (oil spill, natural film, ice, etc.). There are two main mechanisms that make ocean fronts and eddies visible in SAR images:

- The wind-driven capillary waves will change amplitude and/or direction at a current shear/ convergence/ divergence front. The resulting change in backscatter will show these fronts as dark or bright lines in the radar image. In many cases a current front is also associated with a sea surface temperature (SST) front. Different SST has impact on the boundary layer stability which may induce a change in the background backscatter from one side of the front to the other.
- Surface slicks will often decrease capillary wave amplitude in low-wind conditions (the oil on water effect). If slicks containing organic material are found in the shear and convergence zones in a current front or in an eddy, they will act as a tracer of the position of these zones, and especially of the form of the eddy. This phenomenon is shown in e.g. ESA's SAR ocean feature catalogue. The background brightness is normally uniform for these slicks, but since it depends on the local wind, it may fall below instrument threshold, making the slick effect invisible in the lowest wind parts of the image.

Capillary wave-change-by-current and slick material concentrations will generate backscatter changes which identify the position of the current features. The speed of the surface currents cannot be derived, but time series of images can show displacement of fronts and eddies. In practice ERS SAR data are not feasible for feature tracking since the shortest revisit period at 65°N is 3 days. Even with the one day revisit time, which was demonstrated during the ERS tandem operation from September 1995 to June 1996, it has been found that the same feature can be identified in only 20% of the cases studied. With ASAR Wideswath images, the revisit time for a given area will be higher than for ERS, and it will increase with increasing latitude. In other regions at lower latitudes, the eddies of importance for high current velocities have larger dimensions and longer lifetime, suggesting that they are more favourable for monitoring by satellite image data.

There are two major categories of processes, which are observable in SAR images over ocean: (1) atmospheric boundary layer processes (wind, precipitation), and (2) ocean surface processes (surface waves, fronts, currents, sea ice). SAR can also provide information on specific features such as slicks, bathymetry and location of ships. In this study, only ocean current features are analysed.

There is a strong coupling of atmospheric and sea-surface processes observed in SAR images. Current fronts are observable because the wind generated capillary waves are modulated by the front. In moderate wind, most surface features are observable due to the wind modulation effect. In low wind and with biological surface material present (characteristic for the summer period), most features are observable because slicks act as tracers of converging fronts, shears and of eddies.

Examples of eddies in ERS-1 SAR images are shown in Figure 15, along with the corresponding SAR backscatter profiles and coincident SST from AVHRR image.

Figure 15. (a) NOAA AVHRR SST image where red indicates warmer water in the coastal current and blue is colder Atlantic water; (b) and ERS-1 SAR image from 3 October 1992 showing eddies and current fronts off the western coast of Norway, and a backscatter profile along the thick black line. Note that current fronts can appear both as peaks and troughs in backscatter profiles.

There are some criteria which are used for separation of current fronts and eddies from other features with similar SAR signatures. The most important is to identify wind fronts which are characterised by a generally higher backscatter level on one side of the front compared to the other, while ocean fronts are characterised by line features (dark or bright) with a more homogenous background.

Other criteria are related to the sizes and shapes of the fronts. Wind fronts are usually larger in extent and have less curvature than ocean fronts. Ocean fronts related to eddies may have a smaller scale and stronger curvature, but there are exceptions in the cases of rain showers and local wind gusts, where scales and shapes can be similar to ocean fronts.

5.2 SAR SERVICE CHAIN FOR EDDY TRACKING

The processing and analysis steps for SAR eddy tracking is shown in Fig. 16.

Figure 16. Service chain for SAR eddy tracking

5.3 EXPECTED IMPROVEMENTS IN EDDY TRACKING WITH ENVISAT

With ENVISAT ASAR supported by MERIS and AATSR, it is envisaged that the eddy tracking capability implemented in world-wide services will be significantly improved, as shown in the ground cover map of these sensors (Fig. 14). The most important improvements to be expected from ENVISAT ASAR are:

- Ability to cover larger areas with Wide Swath or Global Monitoring Mode, facilitating the localisation of eddies upstream of the operation site;
- Increased revisit time which makes it possible to have observations every two days at 70 N and every 3 days at 60 N;
- Capability to select incidence angle from 15 degrees to 45 degrees, which is important for detection capability because it gives better flexibility to observe with the optimal incidence angle;
- Simultaneous observations with MERIS and partly AATSR which increases the possibility to observe fronts, eddies and current structures.
- In cloudless areas, MERIS and AATSR can be used alone to detect eddies, with the advantage of wider swaths.
- On-board storage of data which makes it possible to obtain data outside the station mask of existing ground stations.

5.4 PERSONNEL AND RESOURCES

At NERSC one SAR expert will use 2 – 3 hours for ordering, processing and delivery of the SAR eddy map as described in Fig. 16. The product consists of geolocated SAR image and eddy annotation as shown in Fig. 7b. The work will be repeated on days when SAR images are obtained over the study area. For west Scotland this will typically be every three days with use of ENVISAT Wideswath images. The processing is done using NERSC Unix Workstation. Data transmission will take place using “ftp” both for the downloading of unprocessed images from Tromsø Satellite Station and for delivery of products to Fugro GEOS Data Warehouse.

6. STATUS OF SERVICE CHAIN FOR MODEL PRODUCTS FROM NERSC

The model service to be provided by NERSC is described in detail in chapter 4 of the D3 document and will only be reviewed briefly in this chapter. The model system is current set up to be used in the operational forecasting to be carried out as part of the service trial in 2003. Hindcast simulations will not be demonstrated in the service trials.

6.1 INPUT DATA

- Atmospheric forcing data will be obtained from ECMWF. These data can be used under the present agreement for demonstration in the service trial. The agreement must be re-negotiated for commercial use.
- Remote sensing data will be gridded Sea Level Anomalies (SLA) and Sea Surface Temperature (SST) will be assimilated into the model system every 7 days
- In situ data: Current profile measurements from ADCP onboard a platform in principle be assimilated into the model. However, it is better to assimilate point measurements of temperature and salinity, but these data will not be available for the service trials. At the moment there is no data supply from the platform supplying these data into the modelling system at NERSC. This will be developed at a later stage if needed. In the service trial the ADCP data will have an important role as validation data for the model results
- Bathymetry: standard global bathymetry data are used: GTOPO5/GTOPO2

6.2 THE MODELLING AND ASSIMILATION SYSTEM

A number of specific tasks are in progress as part of the preparation and establishment of the forecasting system for the Gulf of Mexico. The status of the work in these tasks as of 25 November 2002 are:

Task 1. Define time cycles of the monitoring/forecasting for the Gulf of Mexico

- Obtain an environmental overview of the area and determine processes to be forecasted
 - Select time cycles in the monitoring and forecasting system to resolve typical processes
- Completed task. Eddies have relatively slow evolution in this region, as shown in Fig. 17 where examples of model simulations and altimeter products with two weeks interval show characteristic temporal and spatial variability. Forecasts will be produced every 7 days and delivered to Fugro GEOS who will send the results to a platform operated by Shell in Gulf of Mexico.

Task 2. Model coverage and grid

- Determine the model grid for the large-scale model and the nested high-resolution model, taking into account location of in situ current moorings, which can provide validation data.
- Set up the high resolution model nested with the large-scale model

Completed task: The large-scale model will have a resolution of 20 – 30 km and the regional high-resolution model in the Gulf of Mexico will have grid cells of about 5 km.

Task 3. Prepare for assimilation of data into the forecasting system

- SST and SLA data will be assimilated into the large scale model as before, but with new data from ENVISAT and JASON contributing to the SST and SLA fields.
- Plan assimilation of available in situ data and decide if the data are useful for assimilation or should be used for validation only.
- Prepare for assimilation into the regional model using Ensemble OI.

This work is ongoing, SST and SLA fields will be included during testing and adjustment. Software for including in situ data is ready, and will be tested first on the large scale model. Assimilation in the regional model is ready.

Task 4. Testing and adjustments of the forecasting system.

- Carry out test runs of the forecasting system.
- Compare output from the test runs by comparing the results with in situ measurements and EO data.
- Interact with customers to make sure that the system will meet their requirements
- Make necessary adjustments of the system.
- Prepare for the service trial experiment, including delivery of products to FG Data Warehouse

This work is ongoing and will continue until start of service trial. Examples of model simulation s in the Gulf of Mexico are shown in Fig. 17 a, b and c.

Task 5: Clarify usage of atmospheric forcing data for the forecasting service

- Two candidate providers of global atmospheric forcing data are ECMWF and NCEP. The terms for use of their atmospheric data for commercial services need to be defined.
- If needed, other providers need to be contacted to define their prices for atmospheric data.

This is clarified with regards to the service trials, which will have status as demonstration. This means that current agreement with ECMWF can be used. For commercial projects, new agreements with a ECMWF or other supplier must be made.

Task 6: Implementation of service trial in the Gulf of Mexico

This is planned to start in March – April 2003 and last for tentatively 3 months.

6.3 PERSONNEL AND RESOURCES

4 persons are involved in the development phase including preparation and implementation of the service trial. Later, it is planned to have 2 persons running the system when it is in operational mode. In addition, 2 persons will be needed for further development of the modelling and forecasting system.

The modelling system is run on an IBM supercomputer in Bergen.

6.4 COMPARISON OF MODEL AND ALTIMETER RESULTS IN GULF OF MEXICO

Figure 17. Example of model simulations (a, b, c) and MSLA products (d, e, f) Gulf of Mexico.

A qualitative comparison of the NERSC model simulations and the CLS altimeter products obtained with two weeks interval is shown in Fig. 17. The model simulations and the altimeter products are not from the same period, so any quantitative comparison is not possible. The altimeter products is Mean Sea Level Anomaly and Geostrophic Velocity from Topex-Poseidon, ERS-2 and Geosat-Follow-On obtained weekly in May 2002. The model simulations are from April – May 1996. It is noteworthy that both the model simulations and the altimeter products show a major cyclone and a major anticyclone, both with diameter of about 300 km, propagating slowly in the center of the Gulf. The sense of rotation is not consistent in the two data sets, however they are from different years.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The initial user requirements for oceanographical information, described in chapter 1 of D3, can be satisfied by the EMOFOR service as listed in Table 7 and 8.

Table 7. Monitoring and forecasting regional processes by EMOFOR service

Regions for service trials	Oceanographic processes and features	How EMOFOR service components can satisfy user requirements
Northwest Europe	Mesoscale eddies & meanders	<p><i>Eddy tracking with EO data</i>, combining altimeter, SAR and optical/IR images, is expected to help in detection and maximum currents associated with the eddies. The eddies are relatively small and propagate fast in this region. Use of EO data for upstream detection has not been tested in this region before. The service trial in west Scotland will be important for assessing the capability of EO data for such detection.</p> <p><i>In-situ current data</i> are necessary to obtain quantitative measurements of current speed and direction at different depths in the water column. The data will be important for verification of features observed by EO data. Current measurements are usually obtained only in key locations, such as from platforms. Spatial variability in the current fields are not available by this method.</p> <p>Modelling of eddies and meanders can be done using a high-resolution model (2 – 5 km grid cells) providing statistical information such as eddy scales (horizontally and vertically), velocities, propagation and distribution probability. Exact modelling of individual eddies and prediction of specific events is not possible.</p>
	Slope current intensification	Modelling and in-situ current measurements are the most useful methods. EO data are not expected to give direct information. The service trial will be used to assess the capability of EO data to provide useful information
Gulf of Mexico	Loop Current eddies	EO data have shown good capability to detect these large eddies (scale 300 km) which move slowly and lasts for many months. Both altimeter and IR/optical images will be useful. Examples of altimeter maps are shown in Fig. 17 d, e and f. Modelling of these eddies is also very promising, as shown in the preliminary test (Fig. 17 a, b and c). The capability to forecast the eddies will be tested in the service trial.
	Near bed intensification	In-situ measurements and modelling are the most useful methods. Model capability will be assessed by comparison with in situ data. Surface information from EO data are not relevant.
	Sub-surface jets	In-situ measurements and modelling are the most useful methods. The capability of the model to simulate the sub-surface jets will be assessed if this phenomenon occurs during the service trial.

Table 8. Specific requirements for EMOFOR service during the operational phase

Operational Phase	Tasks	Example of EMOFOR service components that will be important for decision making
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positioning • FPSO orientation • Subsea installation e.g. riser connection • Pipeline laying 	Mooring/anchor handling ROV/diver activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up-to-date forecasts and real time monitoring of current speed and direction through water column. Model prediction in combination with in situ measurements and EO monitoring will supply important information • Threshold exceedence statistics. Both modelled and observed time series of currents will be used for this statistics.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Routine subsea intervention/maintenance • On-going hydrocarbon production 	ROV/diver activity Fatigue/load/VIV monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same as above

ROV: Remotely-operated vehicle
 FPSO: Floating, Production Storage, Offloading vessel
 VIV: Vortex-induced vibration

Quality assessment of the service will be defined in co-operation with the companies involved in the

Service trials: Shell and BP. The assessment will be made against the following quality criteria that were used in the design of the service components

Reliability: The service must be delivered regularly and on time. Therefore, it is important that data from several satellites are used, avoiding gaps if one satellite fails to deliver data. It also means that in situ data and modelling must be provided because there are parameters which cannot be observed from space, such as deep water currents.

Accuracy: The service must make realistic estimates of present and future conditions. A specific measurement accuracy is not defined. It is like weather forecasting where a certain predictive skill is needed. For example 70 % of the forecasts should be correct in order to be a useful service.

Flexibility: Ad-hoc requests for information made in response to operational needs or rapidly changing conditions must be delivered.

Expandability: The service must be easily adaptable to new geographical regions. The service chain must also be capable of simultaneously servicing several clients in different locations.

Communication: the service product must be easily communicable to offshore personnel as well as those in land-based offices.

Presentation: The product must be tailored to meet the needs of non-oceanographers. This has direct implications for the means by which the service product is delivered to the client.

Cost: The service must appear cost-effective to the customer.